

Bilag: Arbejdsgruppe B – Overblik over Data Management Plan Tools

Data Management Plan Tools

[Argos](#): ARGOS is the joint effort of OpenAIRE and EUDAT to deliver an open platform for Data Management Planning that addresses FAIR and Open best practices and assumes no barriers for its use and adoption.

[DAMAP](#): Austrian tool for machine actionable Data Management Plans.

[DMPTool](#): Widely used tool and many universities or institutes provide a DMPTool instance to researchers.

[DSW](#): Publicly available open-source tool to collaboratively compose data management plans through smart and customisable questionnaires with FAIRness evaluation.

[DeiC DMP](#):

[DMP Canvas Generator](#): Mainly for researchers in Switzerland, is based on a questionnaire following the structure of the SNSF (Swiss National Science Foundation) instructions for DMP submission. Each Swiss High School can develop a specific template/canvas.

[DMPRoadmap](#): DMP Roadmap is a Data Management Planning tool. Management and development of DMP Roadmap is jointly provided by the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/>, and the University of California Curation Center (UC3), <http://www.cdlib.org/services/uc3/>. The DMPTool and DMPonline sites are both now running from the joint DMPRoadmap codebase.

[Easy.DMP](#): Tool provided by the pan-European network EUDAT.

[RDMO](#): The Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) supports research projects in the planning, implementation and administration of all research data management tasks.

Kilde: https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_management_plan